

Forgeries and Networks (ForNet). The *Mitteilungen des Museen-Verbandes* and forgery networks in the 20th century

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Overview

The DFG-funded ForNet¹ project analyzes the *Mitteilungen des Museen-Verbandes* (1899-1939),² a publication by the “International Association of Museum Officials” (“Internationaler Verband von Museumsbeamten zur Abwehr von Fälschungen und unlauterem Geschäftsgebaren”), founded in 1898, to reconstruct historical networks of art forgery and institutional secrecy. This poster presentation focuses on the methodological framework that we have developed to turn archival data into semi-structured data. This enables network analysis to be performed, which in turn leads to further archival research. By creating XML transcriptions from digitized source materials and importing them into a graph database, the project enables the examination of personnel networks, organizational structures, and forgery-related actor constellations. The study uses advanced network analysis techniques to reveal decision-making processes, key individuals, and the interplay between institutional expansion and the detection of forgeries.

Source

In the *Mitteilungen*, members of the “International Association of Museum Officials” reported in individual entries on incidents of possible forgeries, and warnings were issued regarding forgers and dubious figures in the art market. The journal was circulated within the Association and was available exclusively to members; furthermore, the information contained in the *Mitteilungen* was to be treated as strictly confidential.³ With more than 400 members by 1936—including institutions

¹ <https://forgeries-and-networks.github.io/ForNetWeb/>

² <https://digi.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/diglit/mitmusverb>

³ Many issues of the *Mitteilungen* begin with a clause requiring members to return all documents upon leaving the association or upon their death. This underscores the organization’s culture of secrecy.

from Germany, France, Belgium, the Netherlands, the UK, and the US—the Association facilitated cross-border communication on art forgery cases. While some contested works were later rehabilitated, others remain mislabeled as originals in museum collections today (Keazor, 2011). ForNet seeks to reconstruct these obscured histories, situating them within contemporary debates on museums’ roles in knowledge production (Hoppe, 2024). From the 34 volumes of the *Mitteilungen*, we were able to identify 813 entries from the members of the Association. These mention more than 3,300 works of art, 1,700 individuals, 800 institutions, 1,000 events and 950 sources (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Entities in the dataset

Methodology

The manually made XML transcriptions of the digitized *Mitteilungen* (Heidelberg University Library), created at the start of the project, serve as the foundation for structured data extraction. A defined workflow – developing Python scripts to extract data from XML transcriptions and structure them into CSV files, and finally ingesting those into a graph database (Kuczera et al., 2019) – enables historical network analysis. These include personnel networks, used to analyze decision-making and recruitment strategies (Neal, 2023), as well as forgery networks informed by methodologies from criminal network analysis (Bright et al., 2021; Perliger and Pedahzur, 2011), such as traditional centrality metrics coupled with hierarchical clustering of network subgroups and aided by network visualizations.

Expected Outcomes

The analysis will identify the key individuals and institutions involved in forgery networks, map the traditional mechanisms of network formation (Rivera et al., 2010), and evaluate the effectiveness of the Association’s efforts in detecting forgeries. By correlating personnel with forgery networks, the project will shed light on the influence of institutional dynamics on the identification and handling of counterfeits.

Significance

This endeavour demonstrates how digital methods can guide archival research by revealing hidden patterns that remain obscured in traditional analysis. Through an iterative, interdisciplinary workflow, where digital insights inform archival investigation and vice versa, we showcase the value of collaboration across infrastructure providers, digital humanities and art history. The poster will stimulate discussion on how to implement digital tools for historical network analysis as well as their broader implications for understanding knowledge production in museological contexts.

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